

ANALYTIC CONTINUATION OF THE ℓ -GENERALIZED FIBONACCI ZETA FUNCTION

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Abstract

In this paper, for any positive integer $\ell \geq 2$, we define the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function. We then study its analytic continuation to the whole complex plane \mathbb{C} . Further, we compute a possible list of singularities and residues of the function at these simple poles. Moreover, we deduce that the special values of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function at negative integer arguments are rational.

1. Introduction

Let $\ell \geq 2$ be an integer. The n^{th} ℓ -generalized Fibonacci sequence $(F_n^{(\ell)})_{n \geq 2-\ell}$ is defined as

$$F_n^{(\ell)} = F_{n-1}^{(\ell)} + F_{n-2}^{(\ell)} + \cdots + F_{n-\ell}^{(\ell)}$$

with the initial conditions

$$F_{-(\ell-2)}^{(\ell)} = F_{-(\ell-3)}^{(\ell)} = \cdots = F_0^{(\ell)} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad F_1^{(\ell)} = 1.$$

Also, $F_n^{(\ell)}$ is called the n^{th} ℓ -generalized Fibonacci number. From [3], we obtain that

$$F_n^{(\ell)} = 2^{n-2} \quad \text{for all} \quad 2 \leq n \leq \ell + 1, \quad \text{and} \quad F_n^{(\ell)} < 2^{n-2} \quad \text{for all} \quad n \geq \ell + 2.$$

The characteristic polynomial of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci sequence is given by

$$\phi_\ell(x) = x^\ell - x^{\ell-1} - \cdots - x - 1. \tag{1}$$

It is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ and has one root outside the unit circle. Let $\alpha = \alpha_1$ be that single root which lies between $2(1 - 2^{-\ell})$ and 2 (see [10]), which is the dominant root of $\phi_\ell(x)$. Let the other roots of the polynomial (1) be $\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_\ell$. When ℓ is an even integer, $\phi_\ell(x)$ has one negative real root which lies in the interval $(-1, 0)$. In 2014, Dresden and Du [4] gave the “Binet-like formula” for the terms $F_n^{(\ell)}$ which is given by

$$F_n^{(\ell)} = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} \frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{n-1}. \tag{2}$$

From [4], it is also known that

$$\left| F_n^{(\ell)} - \frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right| < \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for all } n \geq 2 - \ell.$$

In 2013, Bravo and Luca [2] obtained that

$$\alpha^{n-2} \leq F_n^{(\ell)} \leq \alpha^{n-1} \quad \text{holds for all } n \geq 1 \quad \text{and } \ell \geq 2. \tag{3}$$

When $\ell = 2$, $F_n^{(\ell)}$ is same as the Fibonacci number F_n , and when $\ell = 3$, it coincides with the Tribonacci number T_n .

The *Fibonacci zeta function* is defined by the series

$$\zeta_F(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{F_n^s}, \quad \text{Re}(s) > 0.$$

The analytic continuation of the Fibonacci zeta function was studied by Navas [8] in 2001. The arithmetic nature of the special values of the Fibonacci zeta function and of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ behave similarly. The irrationality of $\zeta_F(1)$ was proved by André-Jeannin [1] in 1989, while the transcendence of $\zeta_F(2m)$, for $m \in \mathbb{N}$, was given by Duverney et al. [5] in 1997. Furthermore, in 2007, Elsner et al. [6] showed that $\zeta_F(2), \zeta_F(4), \zeta_F(6)$ are algebraically independent over \mathbb{Q} . Murty [7] deduced that $\zeta_F(2m)$, for $m \in \mathbb{N}$, is transcendental by using the theory of modular forms and a result of Nesterenko [9].

In this paper, we introduce the *ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function* which is defined by

$$\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(F_n^{(\ell)}\right)^s}.$$

When $\ell = 2$, it is same as the Fibonacci zeta function $\zeta_F(s)$. In this paper, we study the analytic continuation of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function. We also give a list of possible singularities of the function $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ and calculate their residues. Moreover, we discuss the arithmetic nature of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function at negative integer arguments.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we prove that $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ is absolutely convergent in $\text{Re}(s) > 0$. In Section 3, we obtain the analytic continuation of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$, and compute a list of possible poles and their residues. In Section 4, we prove that the special values of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function at negative integer arguments are rational.

2. Preliminaries

Proposition 1. *The infinite series $\sum_{n>0} (F_n^{(\ell)})^{-s}$ converges absolutely in the right half plane $\{s \in \mathbb{C} : \text{Re}(s) > 0\}$.*

Proof. From (3), we get

$$\left| (F_n^{(\ell)})^{-s} \right| = (F_n^{(\ell)})^{-\sigma} \leq (\alpha^{n-2})^{-\sigma} = \alpha^{2\sigma} (\alpha^{-n\sigma}). \tag{4}$$

Since $\sigma = \text{Re}(s) > 0$, from (4), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| (F_n^{(\ell)})^{-s} \right| \leq \alpha^{2\sigma} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\alpha^{-n\sigma}) = \frac{\alpha^{2\sigma}}{\alpha^{\sigma} - 1} < \infty.$$

□

The next lemma tells us that the integer closest to the first term of the Binet-like formula is the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci number.

Lemma 1 (Dresden and Du [4]). *Let $F_n^{(\ell)}$ be the n^{th} ℓ -generalized Fibonacci number. Then*

$$F_n^{(\ell)} = \text{rnd} \left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right) \quad \text{for all } n \geq 2 - \ell,$$

where α is the unique positive dominant root and $\text{rnd}(x) = \lfloor x + \frac{1}{2} \rfloor$ denotes the value of x rounded to the nearest integer.

3. Analytic Continuation of the ℓ -Generalized Fibonacci Zeta Function

Theorem 1. *The ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ can be meromorphically continued to the whole complex plane \mathbb{C} with possible simple poles at*

$$s = s_{k, k_2, \dots, k_\ell, n} = -k + \frac{2ni\pi + k_2 \log \alpha_2 + \dots + k_\ell \log \alpha_\ell}{\log \alpha}, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}, k, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_\ell \in \mathbb{N}_0 \tag{5}$$

such that $k = k_2 + k_3 + \dots + k_\ell$, where \mathbb{N}_0 denotes the set of non-negative integers and $\log(\alpha_i)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$) are the principal values whose imaginary parts lie in the interval $(-\pi, \pi]$. Moreover, the residue of $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ at $s = s_{k, k_2, \dots, k_\ell, n}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{-1} \right)^{-s_{k, k_2, \dots, k_\ell, n}} \binom{-s_{k, k_2, \dots, k_\ell, n}}{k} \left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{-1} \right)^{-k} \\ & \times \frac{k!}{k_2! \cdots k_\ell!} \prod_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{-1} \right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\log \alpha}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Because of Lemma 1 and the fact that $F_n^{(\ell)} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$, we have

$$\left| \left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right) \right| \geq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Therefore, we get that

$$\left| \frac{\sum_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{n-1} \right)}{\left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right)} \right| = \frac{|F_n^{(\ell)} - \frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1}|}{\left| \left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right) \right|} < \frac{1/2}{1/2} = 1.$$

Now, we express

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(F_n^{(\ell)} \right)^{-s} \\ & = \left(\left(\frac{(\alpha - 1)\alpha^{n-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \right) + \sum_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{n-1} \right) \right)^{-s} \\ & = \left(\frac{(\alpha - 1)\alpha^{n-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \right)^{-s} \left(1 + \frac{\sum_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{n-1} \right)}{\left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right)} \right)^{-s} \\ & = \left(\frac{(\alpha - 1)\alpha^{n-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \right)^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s}{k} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{n-1} \right)}{\left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right)} \right)^k. \end{aligned}$$

Using Proposition 1, observe that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| \left(\frac{(\alpha - 1)\alpha^{n-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \right)^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s}{k} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{n-1} \right)}{\left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{n-1} \right)} \right)^k \right| \\ & = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| \left(F_n^{(\ell)} \right)^{-s} \right| < \infty. \end{aligned}$$

On interchanging the order of summation and using the multinomial expansion formula, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(F_n^{(\ell)}\right)^{-s} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(\alpha-1)\alpha^{n-1}}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\right)^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s}{k} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2)}\right)\alpha_i^{n-1}}{\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\right)\alpha^{n-1}}\right)^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s}{k} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(\alpha-1)\alpha^{n-1}}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\right)^{-s} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2)}\right)\alpha_i^{n-1}}{\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\right)\alpha^{n-1}}\right)^k \\ &= \left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\alpha^{-1}\right)^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s}{k} \left\{ \left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\alpha^{-1}\right)^{-k} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \times \sum_{\substack{k_2+\dots+k_{\ell}=k}} \frac{k!}{k_2! \dots k_{\ell}!} \prod_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{(\alpha_i-1)\alpha_i^{-1}}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2)}\right)^{k_i} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\alpha_2^{k_2} \dots \alpha_{\ell}^{k_{\ell}}}{\alpha^{s+k}}\right)^n \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\left|\frac{\alpha_2^{k_2} \dots \alpha_{\ell}^{k_{\ell}}}{\alpha^{s+k}}\right| \leq \frac{\alpha^{k_2+\dots+k_{\ell}}}{\alpha^{s+k}} = \frac{1}{\alpha^{\sigma}} < 1$ for $\sigma > 0$. Therefore, the above series becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s) &= \left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\alpha^{-1}\right)^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{-s}{k} \left\{ \left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\alpha^{-1}\right)^{-k} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \times \sum_{\substack{k_2+\dots+k_{\ell}=k}} \frac{k!}{k_2! \dots k_{\ell}!} \prod_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{(\alpha_i-1)\alpha_i^{-1}}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2)}\right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\alpha^{s+k}\alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_{\ell}^{-k_{\ell}} - 1} \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

From (2), it is clear that for any integer i with $1 \leq i \leq \ell$, we have $2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2) \neq 0$. Note that the function

$$h_{k,k_2,\dots,k_{\ell}}(s) = \frac{1}{\alpha^{s+k}\alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_{\ell}^{-k_{\ell}} - 1}$$

has poles at

$$s = -k + \frac{2ni\pi + k_2 \log \alpha_2 + \dots + k_{\ell} \log \alpha_{\ell}}{\log \alpha}, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad k, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_{\ell} \in \mathbb{N}_0$$

with $k = k_2 + k_3 + \dots + k_{\ell}$.

Consider the function

$$g_{k,k_2,\dots,k_{\ell}}(s) = \alpha^{s+k}\alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_{\ell}^{-k_{\ell}} - 1.$$

Then, we have

$$g'_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell}(s) = \alpha^{s+k} \alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_\ell^{-k_\ell} \log \alpha.$$

Thus, the value of $g'_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell}(s)$ at

$$s = s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n} = -k + \frac{2ni\pi + k_2 \log \alpha_2 + \dots + k_\ell \log \alpha_\ell}{\log \alpha}$$

is $\log \alpha$, which is non-zero. Therefore, the poles of $h_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell}(s)$ are simple.

The series (6) determines a holomorphic function on \mathbb{C} except for the poles derived from the function $h_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell}(s)$. Hence, the function $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ can be meromorphically continued to the whole s -plane and it has the possible simple poles at

$$s = s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n} = -k + \frac{2ni\pi + k_2 \log \alpha_2 + \dots + k_\ell \log \alpha_\ell}{\log \alpha}.$$

Since the residue of

$$h_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell}(s) = \frac{1}{\alpha^{s+k} \alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_\ell^{-k_\ell} - 1}$$

at

$$s = s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n} = -k + \frac{2ni\pi + k_2 \log \alpha_2 + \dots + k_\ell \log \alpha_\ell}{\log \alpha}$$

is

$$\text{Res}_{s=s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n}} h_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell}(s) = \frac{1}{\frac{d}{ds} \left(\alpha^{s+k} \alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_\ell^{-k_\ell} - 1 \right)} \Big|_{s=s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n}} = \frac{1}{\log \alpha},$$

the residue of $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ at $s = s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Res}_{s=s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n}} \zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s) \\ &= \left(\frac{(\alpha - 1)\alpha^{-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \right)^{-s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n}} \binom{-s_{k,k_2,\dots,k_\ell,n}}{k} \left(\frac{(\alpha - 1)\alpha^{-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \right)^{-k} \\ & \quad \times \frac{k!}{k_2! \dots k_\ell!} \prod_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\alpha_i - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \alpha_i^{-1} \right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\log \alpha}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 1. When $\ell = 2$, we have $\alpha\alpha_2 = -1$, and thus $\alpha_2 = \frac{-1}{\alpha}$. Since α is a positive real number, $\arg \alpha_2 = \pi$. From (5), we get that

$$\begin{aligned} s = s_{k,k_2,n} &= -k + \frac{2ni\pi + k \log \alpha_2}{\log \alpha} = -k + \frac{2ni\pi + k \log |\alpha_2| + ik \arg \alpha_2}{\log \alpha} \\ &= -k + \frac{2ni\pi - k \log |\alpha| + ik \arg \alpha_2}{\log \alpha} = -2k + i \frac{2n\pi + k \arg \alpha_2}{\log \alpha} \\ &= -2k + \frac{i\pi(2n + k)}{\log \alpha}. \end{aligned}$$

This is the same list of poles as obtained by Navas [8].

Next, we discuss the special cases of singularities for our better understanding.

Corollary 1. *Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}, k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ such that $(\ell - 1) | k$. Then, the possible poles of $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ are given by*

$$s_{k, \frac{k}{\ell-1}, \dots, \frac{k}{\ell-1}, n} = \begin{cases} -(k + \frac{k}{\ell-1}) + i \frac{\pi(2n + \frac{k}{\ell-1})}{\log \alpha} & \text{if } \ell \text{ is even,} \\ -(k + \frac{k}{\ell-1}) + i \frac{2n\pi}{\log \alpha} & \text{if } \ell \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Proof. Note that $\alpha\alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_\ell = (-1)^{\ell+1}$. Therefore, we have $|\alpha\alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_\ell| = 1$. This implies that

$$\log \alpha + \log |\alpha_2| + \cdots + \log |\alpha_\ell| = 0. \tag{8}$$

Observe that $\alpha > 1$ and for $1 \leq j \leq \ell$, we can write $\log \alpha_j = \log |\alpha_j| + i \arg \alpha_j$, where $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and $\arg \alpha_j \in (-\pi, \pi]$. Since the $\log \alpha_j$'s are principal values of complex logarithms, if ℓ is odd,

$$\arg \alpha_2 + \cdots + \arg \alpha_\ell = 0, \tag{9}$$

and if ℓ is even,

$$\arg \alpha_2 + \cdots + \arg \alpha_\ell = \pi. \tag{10}$$

Now using (8), (9), and (10) in (5) with $k_2 = k_3 = \cdots = k_\ell = \frac{k}{\ell-1} \in \mathbb{N}_0$, we get (7). \square

Remark 2. From Corollary 1, we can see that some of the possible poles lie on the lines $\text{Re}(s) = -(k + \frac{k}{\ell-1})$ spaced at intervals of length $\frac{2\pi i}{\log \alpha}$. In particular, for $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, the possible simple poles of $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ are $s = -(k + \frac{k}{\ell-1})$, when ℓ is odd, and $s = -(k + \frac{k}{\ell-1}) + i \frac{k\pi}{(\ell-1)\log \alpha}$, when ℓ is even. In this section, when ℓ is an even integer and $k = -2n(\ell - 1)$, then from (7), we obtain $s = 2n\ell$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\leq 0}$, which are the possible simple negative integer poles.

4. Special Values at Negative Integer Arguments

Furthermore, we will discuss the values of $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$ at negative integers.

Theorem 2. *Let m be a positive integer such that $-m$ is not a pole of $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$. Then $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m) \in \mathbb{Q}$.*

Proof. Let m be a positive integer such that $-m$ is not a pole of $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(s)$. Then

from (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m) &= \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} \left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{-1} \right)^{m-k} \\ &\quad \times \left(\sum_{k_2 + \dots + k_\ell = k} \frac{k!}{k_2! \dots k_\ell!} \prod_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{(\alpha_i - 1)\alpha_i^{-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\alpha^{-(m-k)} \alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_\ell^{-k_\ell} - 1} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Note that, since $0 \leq k \leq m$, we have $0 \leq m - k \leq m$. Let b be a fixed integer with $0 \leq b \leq m$. If we choose $m - k = b$, then $k = m - b$ and $-m + k = -b$. Then, the coefficient of $\left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \alpha^{-1} \right)^b$ in equation (11) is

$$\binom{m}{m-b} \sum_{\substack{k_2 + \dots + k_\ell \\ = m-b}} \frac{(m-b)!}{k_2! \dots k_\ell!} \prod_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{(\alpha_i - 1)\alpha_i^{-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_i - 2)} \right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\alpha^{-b} \alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_\ell^{-k_\ell} - 1}.$$

Let $\sigma : \mathbb{Q}(\alpha, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_\ell) \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}(\alpha, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_\ell)$ be a non-trivial field automorphism. We know that σ permutes the roots of the irreducible polynomial $\phi_\ell(x)$. We choose r and j ($1 \leq j, r \leq \ell$) such that $\sigma(\alpha) = \alpha_r$ and $\sigma(\alpha_j) = \alpha$. Just for abbreviation, we denote the term $\frac{\alpha_r - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha_r - 2)} \alpha_r^{-1}$ by a_r . Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m)) & \tag{12} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} a_r^{m-k} \left(\sum_{k_2 + \dots + k_\ell = k} \frac{k!}{k_2! \dots k_\ell!} \prod_{i=2}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\sigma(\alpha_i) - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\sigma(\alpha_i) - 2)} \sigma(\alpha_i)^{-1} \right)^{k_i} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \frac{1}{\alpha_r^{-(m-k)} \sigma(\alpha_2)^{-k_2} \dots \sigma(\alpha_\ell)^{-k_\ell} - 1} \right) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} a_r^{m-k} \left(\sum_{k_2 + \dots + k_\ell = k} \frac{k!}{k_2! \dots k_\ell!} \prod_{\substack{i=2 \\ i \neq j}}^{\ell} \left(\frac{\sigma(\alpha_i) - 1}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\sigma(\alpha_i) - 2)} \sigma(\alpha_i)^{-1} \right)^{k_i} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \left(\frac{(\alpha - 1)\alpha^{-1}}{2 + (\ell + 1)(\alpha - 2)} \right)^{k_j} \frac{1}{\alpha_r^{-(m-k)} \sigma(\alpha_2)^{-k_2} \dots \sigma(\alpha_\ell)^{-k_\ell} - 1} \right). \end{aligned}$$

In (12), the coefficient of $\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\alpha^{-1}\right)^b$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=b}^m \binom{m}{k} a_r^{m-k} \left(\sum_{k_2+\dots+k_{j-1}+k_{j+1}+\dots+k_\ell=k-b} \frac{k!}{\left(\prod_{\substack{i=2 \\ i \neq j}}^\ell k_i!\right)} b! \right. \\ & \quad \left. \times \prod_{\substack{i=2 \\ i \neq j}}^\ell \left(\frac{(\alpha_i-1)\alpha_i^{-1}}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2)}\right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\alpha^{-b}\alpha_r^{-(m-k)} \prod_{\substack{i=2 \\ i \neq j}}^\ell \alpha_i^{-k_i} - 1} \right) \\ &= \binom{m}{m-b} \sum_{k=b}^m a_r^{m-k} \frac{1}{(m-k)!} \left(\sum_{k_2+\dots+k_{j-1}+k_{j+1}+\dots+k_\ell=k-b} \frac{(m-b)!}{\left(\prod_{\substack{i=2 \\ i \neq j}}^\ell k_i!\right)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. \times \prod_{\substack{i=2 \\ i \neq j}}^\ell \left(\frac{(\alpha_i-1)\alpha_i^{-1}}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2)}\right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\alpha^{-b}\alpha_r^{-(m-k)} \prod_{\substack{i=2 \\ i \neq j}}^\ell \alpha_i^{-k_i} - 1} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Note that $(m-k) + (k-b) = m-b$. Since k varies from b to m , we have $0 \leq m-k \leq m-b$, and $0 \leq k_i \leq m-b$. Thus, the above sum will be

$$\binom{m}{m-b} \sum_{\substack{k_2+\dots+k_\ell \\ =m-b}} \frac{(m-b)!}{k_2! \dots k_\ell!} \prod_{i=2}^\ell \left(\frac{(\alpha_i-1)\alpha_i^{-1}}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha_i-2)}\right)^{k_i} \frac{1}{\alpha^{-b}\alpha_2^{-k_2} \dots \alpha_\ell^{-k_\ell} - 1}.$$

For any integer b with $0 \leq b \leq m$, we have proved that the coefficient of $\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{2+(\ell+1)(\alpha-2)}\alpha^{-1}\right)^b$ in $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m)$ is equal to that in $\sigma(\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m))$. Therefore, for any field automorphism σ , we have $\sigma(\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m)) = \zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m)$. Hence $\zeta_{F^{(\ell)}}(-m) \in \mathbb{Q}$. □

5. Concluding Remark

Analogous to the Fibonacci zeta function, it is interesting to find the zeros of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function. The study of arithmetic nature of special values of the ℓ -generalized Fibonacci zeta function at positive even integer arguments is another important object for future discussion.

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